

Determination of Thymol in Various Pharmaceutical Formulations by Gas Chromatography

R. T. SANE, V. S. NARKAR, P. P. KARKHANIS and P. G. ANAOKAR

Ramnarain Ruia College, Matunga, Bombay-400 019

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The present work describes a gas chromatographic method to estimate thymol in five different pharmaceutical formulations. Thymol was extracted by chloroform and gas chromatographed using a 2 m × 3 mm I. D. glass column packed with 3% OV-225 on Chromosorb (HP) 80/100 mesh at oven temperature of 170°, injector and detector temperature of 210°. The flow rate of nitrogen (carrier gas) was 32 ml/min., *p*-chlorophenol was used as an internal standard. The amount of thymol found by the proposed gas chromatographic method ranges between 96.1 to 100.2% of the labelled amount. The percent recoveries for different pharmaceutical formulations were found to be between 99% to 101%.

THYMOL is widely used in various pharmaceutical preparations due to its antibacterial and anti-fungal activity. It is also valued for its carminative, stimulant and antispasmodic properties.

Grim and Senjkovic¹ have reported a GLC method to estimate thymol from the extract of thymus vulgaris. Porcaro² and Moshonas³ has described a GLC method to determine thymol from essential oils. Matthew⁴ has described a GLC method to estimate thymol from blood plasma or serum. No GLC method has been reported in literature to detect or estimate thymol in pharmaceutical formulations which are widely used in practice. In the present work we have developed a simple gas chromatographic method to determine thymol in five different commercially available pharmaceutical preparations.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions: Thymol BP, *p*-chlorophenol 99% pure, sodium carbonate AR grade, sodium hydroxide BDH and chloroform chromatographic grade were used. The following solutions were prepared for GLC analysis.

Standard thymol solution: was prepared by dissolving 50 mg of thymol BP in 50 ml of chloroform in a volumetric flask.

Internal standard: About 300 mg of *p*-chlorophenol (PCP) was weighed accurately, dissolved and made to 100 ml with chloroform. In case of cream and ointment *p*-chlorophenol was dissolved in 0.1N sodium hydroxide solution.

Working standard: 1 ml of the standard thymol solution and 1 ml of the internal standard in chloroform were mixed and diluted to 10 ml with chloroform.

Preparation of sample solution for GLC analysis: Sample solutions were prepared from formulations in the forms of tablet, liquid, cream and ointment.

(a) **Tablet:** 20 tablets were crushed, powdered and weight equivalent to two tablets was taken in stoppered flask. 10 ml of chloroform and 20 ml of internal standard solution were added and thymol was extracted in chloroform by vigorous shaking. The mixture was filtered and washed with chloroform. The final volume was adjusted to 50 ml. A 2.5 ml of aliquot was diluted with chloroform to 10 ml.

(b) **Liquid:** A sample equivalent to 2.5 mg of thymol and 5 ml of 5% sodium bicarbonate were mixed well in a separatory funnel. 2.5 ml of internal standard in chloroform and 10 ml of chloroform were added and shaken well. The two layers were allowed to separate and chloroform layer was collected in 25 ml volumetric flask. The aqueous layer was washed twice with 5 ml of chloroform and the washings were added to first extract and the volume adjusted to 25 ml with chloroform.

(c) **Liquid:** A sample equivalent to 6 mg of thymol was taken in a separatory funnel containing 10 ml of water, 25 ml of internal standard in sodium hydroxide was added. The mixture was acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid. This formulation contains 1.2% of free iodine and was removed by adding few drops of sodium thio-sulphate. Thymol was extracted from the mixture by shaking with 25, 10 and 10 ml portions of chloroform. The combined chloroform extract was diluted to 50 ml. 2 ml of aliquot was diluted to 10 ml with chloroform for analysis.

(d) **Cream:** To the sample equivalent to 12 mg of thymol 10 ml of water, 10 ml of 10% sodium hydroxide and 25 ml of internal standard in sodium

hydroxide were added. The mixture was heated on a water bath to melt, mixed well, cooled, filtered and the filtrate diluted to 100 ml with water. 10 ml of the diluted solution was acidified, then sodium carbonate was added to make the solution just alkaline. The alkaline solution was transferred to a separatory funnel and thymol was extracted with successive quantities of 10, 5, 5 ml of chloroform. The combined chloroform extract was diluted to 25 ml with chloroform. In this method thymol was extracted with chloroform in alkaline condition to avoid interference of benzoic acid which was present in the sample.

(e) *Ointment* : Similar procedure as for cream was used. The only difference was that in this case the extraction with chloroform was carried out in acidic condition instead of slightly alkaline one.

Chromatography :

Instrument : Intersmat GC-112 single column gas chromatograph, equipped with flame ionization detector and 1 mv linear recorder was used.

Column : A 2 m x 3 mm I. D., glass column, packed with 3% OV225 on Chromosorb (HP) 80/100 mesh was used for all the determinations.

Operating conditions : Column oven temperature 170°, detector and injection port temperature 210°. The flow rate of carrier gas (nitrogen), hydrogen and air were 32 ml/min, 20 ml/min and 400 ml/min respectively. About 1 µl of working standard solution and sample solutions were injected using 10 µl Hamilton syringe. From the chromatograms the peak heights of thymol and PCP (internal standard) were measured and the amount of thymol were calculated as below :

mg thymol/g or ml of the formulation

$$= \frac{hs \times Rx \times A \times D}{hx \times Rs \times W}$$

where, hx—Peak height of PCP in the chromatogram of sample.

hs—Peak height of thymol in the chromatogram of sample.

Rx—Peak height of PCP in chromatogram of standard solution.

Rs—Peak height of thymol in the chromatogram of standard solution.

A—mg/ml of thymol in standard solution.

W—Weight in g or volume in ml of the formulation taken for analysis.

D—Dilution factor introduced due to the preparation of the sample solution.

Recovery Experiment :

To fixed aliquots of sample solution, the thymol content of which are already determined by the present method, were added three different known levels of thymol, and total amount of thymol per ml or g were determined. Seven repetition measurements per level of added thymol were made. Recovery, which is the difference between thymol found and thymol already present in the aliquot, was expressed as percentage of added thymol, and is given by the equation

% Recovery =

$$\frac{(\text{Thymol found} - \text{Thymol already present}) \times 100}{\text{Thymol added.}}$$

The average of these results with standard deviation is present in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Chromatograms of Chloroform Extracts of Tablet (—), Liquid (----) and Cream (-.-.-) after suitable treatment.

TABLE 1—AMOUNT OF THYMOL IN DIFFERENT PHARMACEUTICAL FORMULATIONS AS DETERMINED BY THE PRESENT METHOD

Formulations	Thymol present (as per label)	Thymol found (as percentage of labelled amount)	Thymol recovered (as percent of added amount)
Liquid	0.06%	98 ± 0.5%	100 ± 0.5%
Liquid	0.23%	96 ± 1.0%	99 ± 1.0%
Tablet	5.4 mg/tab	100 ± 1.5%	99 ± 1.5%
Cream	0.5%	96 ± 1.1%	99 ± 1.1%
Ointment	1.0%	99 ± 1.2%	101 ± 1.2%

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 represents typical chromatograms of extracts of tablets, liquid and cream with added internal standard. The facts that peaks due to thymol and the internal standard (PCP) are well resolved and are not interfered by peaks due to other chemicals extracted along with thymol show the adequacy of the internal standard used and the chromatographic conditions and the column chosen for the analysis. Similar chromatograms were obtained with other formulations examined. When the formulations were directly extracted with chloroform and analysed by GLC, serious interference with the thymol and PCP peaks by those due to ingredients like menthol, salicylic acid,

benzoic acid, boric acid, camphor, methyl salicylate, cinnamon oil and eucalyptus oil etc. present in the formulation occurred. This interference could be removed by the sample treatments of the sample, as described with Experimental section, before the extraction of thymol by chloroform. The proposed method is quick and simple, GLC peaks were sharp accurate results could be calculated from peak heights. Accuracy of the results is reflected in their closeness with those declared by the manufacturers in the label (Table 1). Almost quantitative recovery of thymol from a range of pharmaceutical formulation by the extraction procedure (Table 1) shows that the present method can be profitable used in routine analysis of thymol in similar formulations.

References

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